

CORRELATIONAL STUDY OF QUALITY OF LIFE AND DIABETES MELLITUS II: EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE AND DIABETES MANAGEMENT OUTCOMES

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes has become a serious threat to people's health. In recent years, the number of diabetic patients has gradually increased. It has the characteristics of a long course of disease, high incidence and easy occurrence of complications. In severe cases, it can lead to multiple organ damage and negatively affect the quality of life of patients. Therefore, the researchers wanted to determine the quality of life of people with diabetes to inform the development of diabetes interventions. This study decided to investigate the relationship between quality of life and disease management outcomes in people with type 2 diabetes, with the aim of providing a basis for developing measures that can improve quality of life in people with type 2 diabetes. The study used the WHO-BREF questionnaire and Spearman correlation analysis to determine statistical significance. There were significant correlations between blood glucose control ($P < 0.01$) and complication prevention ($P < 0.01$) and quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes. The results reveal the importance of controlling blood sugar and preventing complications in improving quality of life for people with type 2 diabetes.

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus , quality of life, disease management, patients with diabetes*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a metabolic disorder caused by genetic and environmental factors, resulting in insulin insensitivity, insulin deficiency, and impaired biological function. Due to the high prevalence of diabetes and the associated disability and mortality, the disease has become a critical health issue worldwide. According to data from the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) in 2021, approximately 537 million adults worldwide have diabetes, with a prevalence of 10.5%, and three-quarters of those living with diabetes live in low - and middle-income countries. If countries do not take appropriate measures in time, the total number of people with diabetes worldwide is expected to increase to 643 million by 2030, with the prevalence rising to 11.3%. Since the 21st century, diabetes has become one of the most important chronic non-communicable diseases in China, seriously affecting the quality of life of residents (Guariguata et al., 2014). IDF data show that in 2021, China ranks first in the world in the number of people with diabetes, Chinese adults with diabetes reached 141 million, accounting for 24% of the global diabetes patients. Among the various types of diabetes, type 2 diabetes is the main diabetes in the Chinese population, accounting for 93.7% of the total number of diabetes patients (Zheng et al., 2020). The incidence of diabetes is on the rise globally. According to a newly released epidemiological survey, the prevalence of type 2 diabetes among Chinese adults has increased from 11.2% in 2018 to 12.8% in 2023, showing an upward trend.

With the rapid development of China's economy, the acceleration of urbanisation, the increasingly serious ageing of the population and the prevalence of obesity, diabetes has become one of the major public health problems affecting the health of Chinese residents (Tang & Peng, 2023). Diabetes is a metabolic disease characterised by hyperglycemia, which is caused by the inability to reduce blood sugar due to the impaired metabolic function of the human body (Li, 2023). Diabetes is divided into type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM II), gestational diabetes and other diabetes. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is the deficiency or abnormal function of insulin secretion in the human body, resulting in the relative or absolute insufficiency of insulin in the body, which leads to the reduction of glucose uptake and utilization.

The health management of diabetes plays an important role in the treatment process, which is mainly reflected in the prevention and control of blood sugar, diet, medication, exercise and so on (Gao, 2023). Studies have shown that the management results of diabetes patients in China are poor, which is reflected in poor blood sugar control, inadequate blood sugar monitoring, lack of exercise and poor awareness of foot care (Liang, 2020). Now diabetes has become a chronic disease that endangers the physical and mental health of patients. If the blood sugar is not well controlled, it will cause corresponding complications, such as diabetic foot, retinopathy, etc., which will affect their work and seriously affect their quality of life (Zhuang et al, 2021). Diabetes health management through various methods to improve patients' cognitive level, enhance cooperation in the treatment process, change bad living and eating habits, so that patients with diabetes have the ability to regulate diet, exercise and drug treatment, so as to improve treatment compliance, control the disease, reduce or delay the occurrence of

diabetes complications, improve the quality of life of patients(Li, 2020). Therefore, it is an urgent problem to improve the health management level of type 2 diabetes patients, improve their blood sugar control level, improve their physical and mental health, reduce the risk of complications of diabetes patients, and thus improve the quality of life. Through relevant research, the researchers of this study aimed to investigate and statistically analyze the disease management outcomes and quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes in Qufu People's Hospital, provide a theoretical basis for the direction and focus of clinical nursing education, formulate reasonable education plans, and improve education effectiveness, in order to achieve the goal of improving the overall quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the relationship between quality of life and disease management outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Guided by the overall objective, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. To describe the respondents according to their socio-demographic characteristics
2. To identify the respondents' Diabetes mellitus II management outcomes in terms of:
 - a. Glycemic control
 - b. Treatment adherence, and
 - c. Complication prevention;
3. To assess the overall health-related Quality of Life of respondents with Diabetes mellitus II according to:
 - a. Physical,
 - b. Environmental,
 - c. Social, and
 - d. Psychological.
4. To determine the relationship between health-related Quality of Life and Diabetes mellitus II management outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

1. Study design and local

This study mainly explores the relationship between health-related quality of life and diabetes management outcomes. Because it studies the relationship between two variables, this is a descriptive-correlational study. For this study, researchers determined the demographic characteristics, blood sugar control, complication prevention, treatment compliance, and quality of life of the participants. The study was conducted in the Endocrinology Ward of Qufu People's Hospital, which is an authoritative tertiary general hospital in the local area. The hospital has 1,200 beds and is also equipped with a variety

of equipment. The researchers focused on the behavior of the participants in their natural environment without any manipulation of the variables in the study.

2. Study participants

2.1. Sample Size and Sampling

The sample size is measured because the sample population is representative of the total population of the study. The target number of participants for the study was calculated using the Raosoft® tool. Considering the unknown size of the population, a margin of error of 5%, a confidence level of 95%, and a response distribution of 50%; the researcher calculated that the recommended minimum size is 377 participants. The researcher used a convenience sampling method to obtain the sample for this study. This is a non-probability sampling method in which the researcher randomly selects respondents at a specific time and in a specific hospital for research purposes. This sampling method was simpler and faster to implement.

2.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The researchers included a total of 377 people with type 2 diabetes who met the diagnostic criteria of the 2018 Chinese Type 2 Diabetes Prevention and Treatment Guidelines, had a disease course of ≥ 3 months, were over 18 years old, were local residents, and could communicate correctly and express their true feelings and wishes. Patients with mental disorders, cognitive disorders who could not cooperate to complete the answer sheet, and those with severe acute and chronic complications and other serious heart, brain, lung, and kidney diseases were excluded.

3. Research Instruments

This study mainly used questionnaires as a research tool. According to the variables of this study, the researchers set 9 questions to collect the basic socio-clinical demographic information of the patients, set 2 questions to obtain the data of complications through their views on the control of glycemic index, set 4 questions to collect the blood sugar control status of the patients, and used R studio version 4.2.1 software to describe the answers to these 15 questions.

The World Health Organization Brief Table On Quality of Life Measurement was used. This is a 26-item self-directed multiple-choice questionnaire with the following evaluative components: General QOL (one question); HRQOL (one question); Physical Domain (7 questions): Activities of daily living; Dependence on medical substance and medical aids; Energy and fatigue; Mobility; Pain and discomfort and Sleep and rest; Work capacity ; Psychological Domain (6 questions): Bodily image and appearance; Negative feelings; Positive feelings; Self-esteem; Spirituality/ religion/ personal beliefs, Thinking, learning, memory, and concentration; Social Relationship Domain (3 questions): Personal Relationships ;Social Support; Sexual Activity ; Environmental Domain (8 questions):

Financial Resources ; Freedom, physical safety, and security; Health and social care: accessibility and quality ;Home environment; Opportunities for acquiring current information and skills; Participation in opportunities for recreation and leisure activities ; Physical environment (pollution, noise, traffic, climate); Transport.

The World Health Organization Brief Table On Quality of Life Measurement was translated into Chinese. This questionnaire was used in this study because: the questionnaire has been widely used and validated by the World Health Organization; it provides a comparison of quality of life between different diseases; no subject would encounter any difficulty in filling out the questionnaire; it can be used for all types of respondents and the results are wide-ranging; the instrument is also very reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85.

The reliability of the treatment compliance questionnaire in diabetic patients was 0.83. The questionnaire included five dimensions: diet, medication, exercise, self-monitoring and regular review, and the validity of each dimension was 0.85, 0.84, 0.79, 0.78, 0.82, respectively. The questionnaire consists of 20 items in 5 dimensions, and each item adopts a 3-level scoring method, namely: often(1 point), occasionally (2 points), and never (3 points). Questionnaire scores ranged from 20 to 60, with higher scores indicating better patient compliance and lower scores indicating worse patient compliance. In this study, a compliance score of 40 points is taken as the critical point, a compliance score of ≥ 40 points is considered to be good, and a compliance score of < 40 points is considered to be poor.

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The questionnaire will take an estimate of 30 minutes to fill out.

4. Specific Procedures Based on Study Objectives

4.1. Procedure 1: Communication Letters

A letter to the World Health Organization (WHO) was sent to ask permission to use the World Health Organization Brief Table On Quality of Life Measurement; The researchers had obtained approval from the hospital to conduct this study and allowed eligible patients in the hospital to participate in the study. With the approval of the hospital, the researchers signed a confidentiality agreement. The researchers also presented an informed consent form and obtained the consent of the participants.

4.2. Procedure 2: Data Collection

The researcher followed the information provided by the nurse, understood the schedule of the respondents, asked the respondents to fill in the questionnaire, asked the respondents to complete the questionnaire within 30 minutes, collected the questionnaire from the respondents, and checked whether all questions were answered.

4.3. Follow up responses

The respondents had the right to express their withdrawal from the study at any time without any questions; If a participant did not fill out the questionnaire due to doubt, the researcher contacted the participant to explain the questionnaire if necessary, and the participant was informed that there were no right or wrong answers.

5. Statistical Analysis of Data

Guided by the statistician, the R studio version 4.2.1 software was used for data analysis, and the general situation of type 2 diabetes patients was described: the Count data expressed as percentages; Measurement data conforming to normal distribution are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation ($x \pm s$), median and quartile range otherwise. Mean \pm standard deviation was used to describe disease management and quality of life, while Pearson correlation analysis was used to analyze the correlation between disease management and quality of life. If the data did not conform to a normal distribution, Spearman's statistical method was used for analysis. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Blood glucose control and treatment compliance scores of patients with type 2 diabetes were expressed by mean \pm standard deviation ($x \pm s$), the number of complications was expressed by mean \pm standard deviation ($x \pm s$).

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RESULTS

A total of 377 people with diabetes were included in the study. Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents it showed that the demographic characteristics of the respondents in this study indicate a mean age of 64.43 years with a standard deviation of 11.210 years. The sample comprised predominantly male participants (57.82%) compared to females (42.18%). Most respondents were married (76.39%), with smaller percentages being single (4.24%), cohabitation (3.98%), divorced or legally separated (5.57%), and widowed (9.81%). In terms of occupation, a majority were farmers or workers (65.52%), followed by retirees (27.32%), unemployed individuals (6.37%), and students (0.80%). Regarding educational attainment, more than half had completed junior high school or below (55.70%), while others had completed high school or technical secondary school (34.22%), college or undergraduate courses (6.63%), and graduate studies or higher (3.45%). Family history of diabetes mellitus was reported by 38.73% of respondents, while 61.27% reported no such history. The duration of diabetes varied, with 72.41% having had diabetes for less than 10 months, 17.24% for 10-20 months, and 10.34% for more than 20 months. Complications associated with diabetes were reported by many, with 24.93% having no complications, and others suffering from cardiovascular disease (21.49%), cerebrovascular disease (11.67%), eye disease (19.36%), kidney disease (13.53%), and diabetic foot (9.02%). The mean duration of complications varied, with cardiovascular disease lasting on average 5.08 years (SD =

4.612), cerebrovascular disease 3.34 years (SD = 2.011), eye disease 2.51 years (SD = 1.628), kidney disease 3.55 years (SD = 2.703), and diabetic foot 3.65 years (SD = 2.753).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

	M	SD
Age	64.4	
	3	11.210
	n	%
Sex		
Male	218	57.82%
Female	159	42.18%
Civil status		
Single	16	4.24%
Married	288	76.39%
Cohabitation	15	3.98%
Divorce/Legally Separated	21	5.57%
Widow/Widower	37	9.81%
Occupation		
Unemployment	24	6.37%
Student	3	0.80%
Farmer or Worker	247	65.52%
Retirement	103	27.32%
Highest educational attainment		
Junior high school and below	210	55.70%
High school/Technical secondary school	129	34.22%
College/Undergraduate course	25	6.63%
Graduate and above	13	3.45%
Family history of diabetes mellitus		
Yes	146	38.73%
No	231	61.27%
Duration of diabetes (in months)		
less than 10	273	72.41%
10-20	65	17.24%
> 20	39	10.34%
Complications		
None	94	24.93%
Cardiovascular disease	81	21.49%
Cerebrovascular disease	44	11.67%
Eye disease	73	19.36%
Kidney disease	51	13.53%
Diabetic foot	34	9.02%
	M	SD
Years of complication		
Cardiovascular disease	5.08	4.612
Cerebrovascular disease	3.34	2.011

Eye disease	2.51	1.628
Kidney disease	3.55	2.703
Diabetic foot	3.65	2.753

The descriptive statistics on DM II management outcomes in terms of glycemic control showed in Table 2.1. reveal that the respondents had an average last blood sugar level of 11.04 mmol/L with a standard deviation of 3.633 mmol/L. The mean blood glucose concentration two hours after a meal was notably higher at 17.68 mmol/L, with a standard deviation of 3.391 mmol/L. On average, respondents reported their blood sugar levels being higher than normal 5.89 times, with a standard deviation of 3.635. The majority of respondents (82.23%) had undergone fasting blood sugar (FBS) diagnostics, while 17.77% had random blood sugar (RBS) tests. When categorizing the frequency of elevated blood sugar levels, 29.97% of respondents experienced high blood sugar levels more than three times, 25.73% reported elevated levels three to five times, and 44.30% experienced high levels more than five times.

Table 2.1. Descriptive statistics on the DM II management outcomes in terms of Glycemic control.

	M	SD
Last blood sugar (in mmol/L)	11.04	3.633
Blood glucose concentration 2 hours after meal (in mmol/L)	17.68	3.391
Times were blood sugar levels are higher than normal	5.89	3.635
	n	%
Last blood sugar (in mmol/L) category		
Normal	1	0.27%
Impaired fasting glucose	7	1.86%
Provisional diagnosis of diabetes	369	97.88%
Type of blood diagnostics		
FBS	310	82.23%
RBS	67	17.77%
Times were blood sugar levels are higher than normal (in category)		
>3	113	29.97%
3-5	97	25.73%
5 and above	167	44.30%

The descriptive statistics on DM II management outcomes in terms of treatment adherence indicate several areas of concern among the respondents. A significant portion reported often forgetting to take their medicine or inject insulin (49.07%), with 40.05% occasionally doing so. Many respondents were influenced by non-medical staff to change their medication, with 18.57% doing so often and 61.01% occasionally. Nearly half of the respondents (47.75%) often reduced or stopped their medication when symptoms improved, while 31.83% did so occasionally. Conversely, when symptoms worsened or blood sugar levels were high, 38.73% often increased their dosage or changed their medication, and 39.52% did so occasionally. Irregular eating habits were also prevalent, with 23.61% often overeating and 61.80% occasionally doing so. Dietary inflexibility was reported by 16.98% often and 57.82% occasionally. A notable 43.50% often relaxed diet control, substituting exercise with daily activities, and 35.81% occasionally did so. Some

respondents (35.81%) often ate less or no food to control blood sugar, with 42.97% doing so occasionally.

Exercise adherence was also notable, as 18.83% often gave up exercise therapy and 65.25% did so occasionally. Leisure activities such as playing mahjong or watching TV were common, with 22.55% often engaging in these activities and 35.81% occasionally. Monitoring challenges were evident, with 20.16% often failing to monitor themselves during changes in their environment, and 69.50% doing so occasionally. Long-term monitoring lapses were reported, with 35.01% often giving up monitoring for more than a month due to feeling good, and 45.09% doing so occasionally. Regular blood sugar measurement was maintained by most, but 56.23% often did not monitor other critical health indicators. Lastly, hospital visits in response to worsening conditions were frequent, with 67.37% often doing so. Overall, the average treatment adherence score was 37.42 with a standard deviation of 6.985, reflecting considerable variability and highlighting the need for improved adherence strategies in managing DM II.

Table 2.2. Descriptive statistics on the DM II management outcomes in terms of Treatment adherence.

Items	Often n (%)	Occasionally n (%)	Never n (%)	Mean	SD
1. Have you ever forgotten to take medicine or inject insulin?	185 (49.07%)	151 (40.05%)	41 (10.88%)		
2. Have you ever listened to the persuasion of non-medical staff and changed your own drugs?	70 (18.57%)	230 (61.01%)	77 (20.42%)		
3. When you feel that your symptoms have improved or your blood sugar control is better, have you ever reduced your medication or stopped taking it?	180 (47.75%)	120 (31.83%)	77 (20.42%)		
4. When you feel that your symptoms	146 (38.73%)	149 (39.52%)	82 (21.75%)		

are getting worse or your blood sugar level is high, have you ever increased your dosage or changed your medicine?					
5. Do you have any experience of eating at will, overeating and eating irregularly?	89 (23.61%)	233 (61.80%)	55 (14.59%)		
6. Is your diet single and inflexible, and you can't adjust it in time when your illness changes?	64 (16.98%)	218 (57.82%)	95 (25.20%)		
7. Do you relax your diet control whereplace exercise with daily life?	164 (43.5%)	148 (39.26%)	65 (17.24%)		
8. Do you deliberately eat less or no food when	135 (35.81%)	162 (42.97%)	80 (21.22%)		

controlling blood sugar?					
9. Have you ever given up exercise therapy for various reasons?	71 (18.83%)	246 (65.25%)	60 (15.92%)		
10. Do you take playing mahjong and watching TV as your main leisure ways?	85 (22.55%)	135 (35.81%)	157 (41.64%)		
11. Do you often replace exercise with daily life?	107 (28.38%)	134 (35.54%)	136 (36.07%)		
12. Have you ever exercised several times a day or only once a few days?	83 (22.02%)	241 (63.93%)	53 (14.06%)		
13. Do you fail to monitor yourself in time when your internal and external environment changes such as climate change, improper diet, stress and fatigue, and mood swings?	76 (20.16%)	262 (69.50%)	39 (10.34%)		

14. Have you ever given up monitoring for more than 1 month because you feel good?	132 (35.01%)	170 (45.09%)	75 (19.89%)		
15. Do you only measure blood sugar regularly, but do not monitor blood pressure, blood lipid, glycosylated hemoglobin, etc.	212 (56.23%)	133 (35.28%)	32 (8.49%)		
16. Do you not insist on monitoring when you go out, travel or change your lifestyle?	71 (18.83%)	233 (61.80%)	73 (19.36%)		
17. Have you ever forgotten to review?	110 (29.18%)	229 (60.74%)	38 (10.08%)		
18. Do you go to the hospital only when your condition worsens?	254 (67.37%)	98 (25.99%)	25 (6.63%)		

19. Do you think the blood sugar level can be felt by yourself, but you have not checked it as required?	89 (23.61%)	202 (53.58%)	86 (22.81%)		
20. Have you ever had an intermittent review for more than 3 months due to various reasons?	71 (18.83%)	232 (61.54%)	74 (19.63%)		
Overall				37.42	6.985

The descriptive statistics on DM II management outcomes in terms of complication prevention reveal that a significant number of respondents struggle with blood sugar control. Only 8.22% reported having very good control of their blood sugar, while 20.69% described their control as good. A larger proportion, 23.34%, indicated moderate control, and a worrying 37.67% reported poor control, with 10.08% having very poor control. When it comes to the steps taken to manage blood sugar, the majority (63.13%) take their medicine as prescribed, while smaller percentages control their diet (10.88%), exercise moderately (10.88%), and quit smoking (14.32%). A negligible 0.80% reported taking no steps to manage their blood sugar.

Table 2.3. Descriptive statistics on the DM II management outcomes in terms of Complication prevention.

	n	%
How well do you control your blood sugar		
Very good control	31	8.22%
Good control	78	20.69%
Moderate control	88	23.34%
Poor control	14	37.67%
Very poor control	2	10.08%
Steps to take control of blood sugar		
Control diet	41	10.88%

Exercise moderately	41	10.88%
Quit smoking	54	14.32%
	23	
Take medicine as prescribed	8	63.13%
None	3	0.80%

The descriptive statistics on overall quality of life and general health among the respondents indicate a generally low perception of well-being. The average overall quality of life and general health score was 5.52, with a standard deviation of 2.122, reflecting considerable variation in responses. A substantial proportion of respondents rated their quality of life as poor (49.34%) or very poor (6.63%), while 12.47% felt neither poor nor good about their quality of life. On a more positive note, 23.87% were satisfied with their quality of life, and 7.69% were very satisfied. Satisfaction with health was similarly low, with 46.68% rating their health as poor and 9.28% as very poor. Only 10.34% felt neutral about their health, while 26.53% were satisfied and 7.16% very satisfied.

Table 3.1. Overall quality of life and general health.

Items	Very poor n (%)	Poor n (%)	Neither poor and good n (%)	Good n (%)	Very good n (%)	Mean	SD
1.How would you rate your quality of life ?	25(6.63)	186 (49.34%)	47 (12.47%)	90 (23.87 %)	29 (7.69%)		
2.How satisfied are you with your health?	35 (9.28%)	176 (46.68%)	39 (10.34%)	100 (26.53 %)	27 (7.16%)		
Overall						5.52	2.122

The physical health domain of the respondents, as measured by an average transformed scale score of 46.80 with a standard deviation of 17.355, reflects various challenges. Physical pain significantly impacts daily activities for many, with 27.32% reporting it prevents them "very much" and 5.04% indicating an "extreme" impact. Medical treatment is necessary to function for a significant portion, with 21.49% requiring it "very much" and 4.24% to an "extreme" extent. Energy levels are low, as 33.42% feel they have "a little" energy and 7.69% report having none. Mobility is also a concern, with 18.30% rating their

ability to get around as poor, although 32.36% are satisfied with their mobility. Sleep satisfaction is low, with 38.73% dissatisfied and 13.79% very dissatisfied. Satisfaction with daily living activities is mixed, with 25.46% dissatisfied and 10.61% very dissatisfied, while 27.59% are satisfied. Similarly, satisfaction with work capacity varies, with 25.73% dissatisfied and 9.55% very dissatisfied, but 25.46% are satisfied. These findings suggest significant physical health challenges among the respondents, impacting their daily activities, mobility, energy levels, and overall quality of life.

Table 3.2. Physical health domain.

Items	Not all n (%)	A little n (%)	A moderate amount n (%)	Very much n (%)	An extreme amount n (%)	M	SD
3. To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?	16.18 %	36.34%	15.12%	27.32 %	5.04%		
4. How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?	21.22 %	36.34%	16.71%	21.49 %	4.24%		
Items	Not all n (%)	A little n (%)	Moderately n (%)	Mostly n (%)	Completely n (%)	M	SD
10. Do you have enough for everyday life?	7.69%	33.42%	27.59%	20.42 %	10.88%		
Items	Very poor n (%)	Poor n (%)	Neither poor and good n (%)	Good n (%)	Very good n (%)	M	SD
15. How well are	6.90%	18.30%	32.63%	32.36	9.81%		

Items	Very dissatisfied n (%)	Dissatisfied n (%)	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied n (%)	Satisfied n (%)	Very satisfied n (%)	M	SD
you able to get around?				%			
16. How satisfied are you with your sleep?	13.79 %	38.73%	15.65%	23.08 %	8.75%		
17. How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?	10.61 %	25.46%	26.26%	27.59 %	10.08%		
18. How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?	36 (9.55%)	97 (25.73%)	115 (30.50%)	96 (25.46 %)	33 (8.75%)		
Overall						46.80	17.355

The psychological domain of the respondents, reflected by an average transformed scale score of 45.80 with a standard deviation of 21.562, highlights several areas of concern. Enjoyment of life is limited for many, with 13.79% reporting no enjoyment at all and 34.22% enjoying life only a little. However, 27.06% enjoy life very much, and 11.14% enjoy it to an extreme degree. The sense of life being meaningful is similarly varied, with 15.38% feeling life is not meaningful at all and 30.77% feeling it is only a little meaningful, while 26.79% find it very meaningful, and 15.12% to an extreme extent.

Concentration is another challenge, as 13.26% are unable to concentrate at all and 32.10% can concentrate only a little. Meanwhile, 24.93% can concentrate moderately, and 21.49% mostly. Acceptance of bodily appearance is low for many, with 6.37% not accepting it at all and 37.14% accepting it only a little. Moderately and mostly accepting respondents comprise 25.20% and 20.42%, respectively.

Self-satisfaction shows a mixed picture: 7.43% are very dissatisfied, 30.24% are dissatisfied, and 23.61% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. However, 26.79% are

satisfied, and 11.94% are very satisfied. Negative feelings such as blue moods, despair, anxiety, and depression are common, with 18.04% experiencing them quite often, 17.77% very often, and 3.98% always. Nevertheless, 28.65% never experience these feelings, and 31.56% seldom do.

Table 3.3. Psychological domain.

Items	Not all n (%)	A little n (%)	A moderate amount n (%)	Very much n (%)	An extreme amount n (%)	M	SD
5.How much do you enjoy life?	52 (13.79 %)	129 (34.22%)	52 (13.79%)	102 (27.06 %)	42 (11.14%)		
6.To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?	58 (15.38)	116 (30.77%)	45 (11.94%)	101 (26.79 %)	57 (15.12%)		
7. How well are you able to concentrate?	50 (13.26 %)	121 (32.10%)	94 (24.93%)	81 (21.49 %)	31 (8.22%)		
Items	Not all n (%)	A little n (%)	Moderately n (%)	Mostly n (%)	Completely n (%)	M	SD
11.Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?	24 (6.37%)	140 (37.14%)	95 (25.20%)	77 (20.42 %)	41 (10.88%)		
Items	Very dissatisfied n (%)	Dissatisfied n (%)	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied n (%)	Satisfied n (%)	Very satisfied n (%)	M	SD

19. How satisfied are you with yourself?	28 (7.43%)	114 (30.24%)	89 (23.61%)	101 (26.79%)	45 (11.94%)		
Items	Never n (%)	Seldom n (%)	Quite often n (%)	Very often n (%)	Always n (%)	M	SD
26. How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?	108 (28.65%)	119 (31.56%)	68 (18.04%)	67 (17.77%)	15 (3.98%)		
Overall						45.80	21.562

The social relationships domain of the respondents, with an average transformed scale score of 62.67 and a standard deviation of 20.993, indicates a generally positive perception of social interactions and support. Satisfaction with personal relationships is relatively high, with 39.26% satisfied and 15.12% very satisfied, though 2.92% are very dissatisfied and 14.59% dissatisfied. Satisfaction with sex life is similarly positive, with 42.18% satisfied and 10.61% very satisfied, while 4.77% are very dissatisfied and 9.81% dissatisfied. Support from friends is also well-regarded, with 41.64% satisfied and 19.36% very satisfied. However, 5.84% are very dissatisfied and 10.34% are dissatisfied with the support they receive.

Table 3.4. Social relationships domain.

Items	Very dissatisfied n (%)	Dissatisfied n (%)	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied n (%)	Satisfied n (%)	Very satisfied n (%)	M	SD
20. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?	11 (2.92%)	55 (14.59%)	106 (28.12%)	148 (39.26%)	57 (15.12%)		

21. How satisfied are you with your sex life?	18 (4.77%)	37 (9.81%)	123 (32.63%)	159 (42.18%)	40 (10.61%)		
22. How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?	22 (5.84%)	39 (10.34%)	86 (22.81%)	157 (41.64%)	73 (19.36%)		
Overall						62.67	20.993

The results from Table 3.5 shed light on various aspects of individuals' perceptions within the environment domain. Overall, the average environment transformed scale score indicates a moderate level of satisfaction across the surveyed population ($M = 58.05$, $SD = 18.028$). When asked about safety in daily life, a majority (71.26%) reported feeling either very much or extremely safe, while concerns about physical environment health were more evenly distributed, with 51.99% indicating their environment is very much or extremely healthy. However, financial security emerges as a significant issue, with only 29.44% reporting having enough money to meet their needs moderately, mostly, or completely. Access to information and leisure opportunities show moderate satisfaction levels, with 57.91% reporting moderate to complete access to needed information and 64.99% indicating at least moderate opportunities for leisure activities. Satisfaction with living conditions is relatively high, with 54.64% reporting satisfaction or higher, while satisfaction with access to health services and transportation is even higher, with 65.25% and 56.96% expressing satisfaction or higher, respectively.

Table 3.5. Environment domain.

Items	Not at all n (%)	A little n (%)	A moderate amount n (%)	Very much n (%)	An extreme amount n (%)	M	SD
8. How safe do you feel in your daily life?	25 (6.63%)	99 (26.26%)	98 (25.99%)	113 (29.97%)	42 (11.14%)		
9. How healthy is your physical	34 (9.02%)	44 (11.67%)	103 (27.32%)	132 (35.01%)	64 (16.98%)		

environment?)))	%))		
Items	Not all n (%)	A little n (%)	Moderately n (%)	Mostly n (%)	Completely n (%)	M	SD
12. Have you enough money to meet your needs?	38 (10.08%)	140 (37.14%)	88 (23.34%)	72 (19.10%)	39 (10.34%)		
13. How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?	25 (6.63%)	96 (25.46%)	114 (30.24%)	98 (25.99%)	44 (11.67%)		
14. To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?	18 (4.77%)	119 (31.56%)	93 (24.67%)	107 (28.38%)	40 (10.61%)		
Items	Very dissatisfied n (%)	Dissatisfied n (%)	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied n (%)	Satisfied n (%)	Very satisfied n (%)	M	SD
23. How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?	22 (5.84%)	43 (11.41%)	106 (28.12%)	160 (42.44%)	46 (12.20%)		
24. How satisfied are you with your access to health services?	19 (5.04%)	53 (14.06%)	59 (15.65%)	192 (50.93%)	54 (14.32%)		
25. How satisfied are you with your	26 (6.90%)	39 (10.34%)	101 (26.79%)	153 (40.58%)	58 (15.38%)		

transport?							
Overall						58.05	18.028

The correlation analysis between Quality of life (QoL) and type II diabetes (DM II) management outcomes reveals several significant associations. Notably, treatment adherence showed a negative correlation with glycemic control ($r = -0.14, p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher levels of treatment adherence were associated with lowering blood sugar levels. Complication prevention demonstrated a weak positive correlation with glycemic control ($r = 0.10, p < 0.05$), indicating an increase in blood sugar levels for as control for blood sugar levels gets very poorly controlled. A weak negative correlation is also seen for complication prevention and treatment adherence ($r = -0.18, p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher levels of treatment adherence were associated with very good control of blood sugar.

Physical health shows a significant negative correlation with glycemic control ($r = -0.06$, insignificant p-value), complication prevention ($r = -0.48, p < 0.01$) and a weak positive correlation with treatment adherence ($r = 0.09$, insignificant p-value). This indicates that individuals with better physical health tend to lower blood sugar levels, associated with a very good control of blood sugar, and a high treatment adherence. Overall quality of life and general health score shows a significant negative correlation with glycemic control ($r = -0.04$, insignificant p-value), complication prevention ($r = -0.49, p < 0.01$) and a weak positive correlation with treatment adherence ($r = 0.05$, insignificant p-value). This indicates that individuals with better overall quality of life and general health score tend to lower blood sugar levels, associated with a very good control of blood sugar, and a high treatment adherence.

Psychological scores shows a significant negative correlation with complication control ($r = -0.51, p < 0.01$) and a weak positive correlation with treatment adherence ($r = 0.09$, insignificant p-value) and glycemic control ($r = 0.0003$, insignificant p-value). This indicates that individuals with better psychological scores is associated with a very good control of blood sugar. Social relations demonstrate a weak negative correlation with complication prevention ($r = -0.14, p < 0.01$) and with treatment adherence ($r = -0.12, p < 0.05$). Similarly, environmental factors exhibit a moderate negative correlation with complication prevention ($r = -0.28, p < 0.01$) and with treatment adherence ($r = -0.14, p < 0.05$).

Table 4. Correlation analysis between Quality of life and DM II management outcomes.

	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Glycemic control	37 7	11. 04	3.63 3	-						

2. Treatment adherence	37 7	37. 42	6.98 5	- 0.14* *	-					
3. Complicati on prevention a	37 7	-	-	0.10*	- 0.18 **					
4. Overall QoL	37 7	5.5 2	1.12 2	-0.04	0.05	- 0.49 **				
5. Physical health	37 7	46. 80	17.3 55	-0.06	0.09	- 0.48 **	0.61 **			
6. Psycholog ical	37 7	45. 80	21.5 62	0.00 03	0.09	- 0.51 **	0.76 **	0.77 **		
7. Social relations	37 7	62. 67	20.9 93	-0.06	0.12 *	- 0.14 **	0.44 **	0.40 **	0.43 **	-
8. Environm ent	37 7	58. 05	18.0 28	-0.01	0.14 **	- 0.28 **	0.65 **	0.54 **	0.62 **	0.65**

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ^aSpearman correlation coefficient

1 Glycemic control, 2 Treatment adherence, 3 Complication prevention, 4 Overall Quality of Life, 5 Physical health, 6 Psychological, 7 Social relations, 8 Environment

DISCUSSION

Among all 377 T2DM patients in this survey, there were more males than females; the average age was 64.43±11.21 years, and most were over 60 years old. With the rapid development of my country's aging population, the number of elderly patients with diabetes has increased year by year (Huang et al., 2018). In terms of occupation, farmers and workers accounted for the majority; marital status was mostly married (288 cases, 76.39%); in terms of education level, most were high school, technical secondary school or below. Among all the subjects, the average duration of complications was 5.08±4.61 years; most patients had complications, and most had only one complication.

Rose et al. believed that the evaluation criteria for the effect of diabetes treatment include good blood sugar control and improvement of the patient's quality of life. They believed that in the diagnosis and treatment of diabetic patients, attention should not only be paid to blood sugar, but also to the patient's quality of life, so that their lives are as constrained as possible (Rose et al., 2002). Therefore, in addition to biological indicators, the

evaluation of the effect of diabetes treatment should also include the evaluation of quality of life. Quality of life is a set of indicators proposed in the context of the renewal of the medical model to comprehensively measure human health. It is a comprehensive indicator for comprehensively evaluating the individual's physiological, psychological, social functions and material living conditions, and represents the measurement trend of modern health (Fan et al., 1996). It is a multidimensional concept, and its measurement content includes: physiological, psychological state, social relations, environment, spirit, etc. (WHOQoL Group, 1994). Quality of life has become an internationally accepted health evaluation method and is widely used in various fields of medical research.

Quality of life evaluation can provide doctors with comprehensive information from the patient's physiological, psychological, social adaptation and other aspects, quantitatively evaluate the impact of the disease on the patient's health, find its possible influencing factors, and thus take targeted intervention measures. With the research on quality of life, a variety of quality of life assessment scales have been produced at home and abroad, such as the Nottingham Health Scale (NHP), the Comprehensive Quality of Life Questionnaire (GQOL I-74), etc. This study uses the World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire (WHOQOL-100). By using this scale, we can have a deeper understanding of the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes, thereby providing a strong basis for improving their quality of life.

This study showed that the average score of the overall quality of life and overall health status of diabetic patients was 5.52, the average conversion scale score of the physical health dimension was 46.8, the score of the psychological dimension was 45.8, the average score of the social relationship dimension was 62.67, and the environmental score was 58.05. Among these four dimensions, the physical health dimension and psychological dimension scores of diabetic patients were low, and the social relationship dimension score was high, which is contrary to the research results of Chen Ailing (Chen et al., 2006). This may be related to the older average age of the subjects in this study and the fact that the publicity of chronic diseases in my country's health care in recent years has improved the public's awareness of the disease. As the disease progresses, patients with type 2 diabetes gradually develop organ damage, namely diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, etc., which have a greater impact on physical function. At work, we should strengthen the guidance of the behavior of diabetic patients in their lives, encourage their families to actively support and actively participate in the patients' daily lives and disease treatment, and improve the patients' sense of belonging, security and confidence in outpatient continuity treatment.

Diabetes is a long-term chronic disease, and its blood sugar control depends largely on the patient's own understanding of the risk of the disease and the disease control measures taken, as well as how the patient should cooperate with the doctor's treatment. Mastering more diabetes-related knowledge is of great benefit to blood sugar control. The results of this study showed that the treatment compliance level of patients with type 2 diabetes was basically at a medium level, which was higher than the reported data of similar studies in China (Liu et al., 2020; Yu, 2018; Chang, 2018), and most patients had a more serious non-compliance phenomenon. However, patients deviated from the

specific treatment methods. This may also be related to the compliance scale used in this study. Patients with type 2 diabetes need long-term or even lifelong medication to control blood sugar, but long-term medication will not only bring them a greater economic and psychological burden, but also affect the patient's treatment compliance. The average treatment compliance score was 37.42, and medication compliance was higher than other compliance in all dimensions, which may be related to the traditional medical thinking of the Chinese population (Li, & Cai, 2004). It can be seen that patients with type 2 diabetes pay slightly more attention to drug treatment and diet control than exercise therapy, blood sugar monitoring and regular review. The level of compliance directly affects the treatment effect, and medication compliance is one of the key factors affecting the effect of blood sugar control (Li, & Cai, 2004). Therefore, during hospitalization, diabetes education should be strengthened for diabetic patients, and patients should be encouraged to actively participate in various educational activities, such as diabetes education lectures. Emphasizing the importance of persisting in exercise and regular review for disease treatment, and providing one-to-one guidance when discharged from the hospital are all important measures to improve the treatment compliance of diabetic patients. Scientific management of type 2 diabetes not only increases the survival of patients, but also greatly reduces complications such as blindness, disability, cognitive impairment, etc., and improves the quality of life of patients.

Complications and comorbidities are important factors affecting the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes. The number of complications and comorbidities is significantly correlated with the decline in patients' quality of life. The greater the number of complications and comorbidities, the lower the quality of life (Liang et al., 2014). Among them, combined cardiovascular disease significantly affects the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes (Wang et al., 2015). Surveys show that the quality of life of type 2 diabetes patients with cardiovascular disease is significantly lower than that of patients without cardiovascular disease complications (Liu et al., 2016). This is consistent with the results of this study. The gradual progression of diabetes can have an impact on large blood vessels and capillaries. If it is combined with cardiovascular disease, it will accelerate the occurrence of complications of type 2 diabetes. The affected areas include cardiovascular, peripheral nerves, brain, and eyes. Multiple systems or tissues such as the retina, renal microvessels, and feet increase the mortality or disability rate of diabetic patients. Because the complications of diabetes are mostly chronic diseases such as kidney disease, eye disease, and foot disease, the course of the disease is long, the prognosis is poor, and the cost of long-term treatment is high. While the physical functions of type 2 diabetes patients are damaged, their mental state and mental state are also affected. Social functioning can also have serious adverse effects. In addition, if diabetes is not treated properly, some acute complications may occur, such as diabetic ketoacidosis or hyperosmolar nonketotic diabetic coma. Severe acute complications can endanger the patient's life. Therefore, actively controlling and delaying the progression of the primary disease in patients with type 2 diabetes and reducing the probability of

complications and comorbidities are important measures to improve the health of patients with type 2 diabetes.

At present, with the improvement of people's living standards, the aging of society and the change of lifestyle, the incidence of diabetes is gradually increasing ("Guidelines for the Prevention and Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes in China (2017 Edition)", 2018). Diabetes is one of the most common chronic endocrine diseases in the world, which can lead to many short - and long-term adverse outcomes. Diabetic patients have long-term high blood sugar and metabolic disorders, which lead to dysfunction of multiple organs and tissues such as kidneys, blood vessels, nerves, and eyes. As the course of the disease progresses, various complications or complications appear, and their treatment plans become more and more complicated. Although the research on the treatment of diabetes has been continuously deepened for decades, there is still no radical treatment drug. Diabetic patients have been receiving long-term combined treatment of multiple drugs in their lives, and the torture of the disease itself brings great physical and psychological burdens to patients, which seriously affects the quality of life of diabetic patients (Zhang et al., 2018). These complications reduce the quality of life of diabetic patients, aggravate negative emotions, and thus affect treatment compliance, leading to poor control of blood sugar levels. At present, there are about 114 million adult (20-79 years old) diabetics in my country, making it the country with the largest number of diabetics in the world. This means that at least one in every 10 adults is a diabetic. Therefore, the health impact and social medical burden of diabetes cannot be underestimated. Accordingly, it is important to find out the factors that affect the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes.

Quality of life refers to an individual's perception of their physical, emotional and social status (Dickerson, F et al., 2011; Rubin, R.R, et al., 1999). For patients with chronic diabetes, the possibility of complete cure is low. Elderly patients with type 2 diabetes have greater treatment pressure and lower quality of life than healthy people (Neumann, A et al., 2014; Donald, M et al., 2013). In addition, many factors can affect the quality of life of patients. Therefore, understanding and identifying the predictive factors and risk factors of life in patients with type 2 diabetes is of great significance for controlling and delaying the progression of diabetes and preventing the deterioration of the health status and quality of life of diabetic patients. Type 2 diabetes is a chronic metabolic disease, and its occurrence, development and prognosis are closely related to the results of disease management. In this study, the disease management status and quality of life were first evaluated, and the impact of disease management and other factors on quality of life was preliminarily analysed.

Studies have shown that patients with poor self-management levels are associated with more bad behaviors, which can easily affect treatment compliance, increase the risk of complications, aggravate the condition, and affect the patient's quality of life (Ji et al., 2014). It is speculated that the self-management level of patients with T2DM may be related to the quality of life. The results of this study show that overall quality of life and overall health scores are significantly negatively correlated with blood sugar control ($r = -0.04$, p value is not significant), complication prevention ($r = -0.49$, $p < 0.01$), and with

treatment compliance There is a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.05$, p value is not significant). The reason is that diabetic patients with poor disease management often lack health awareness and are often accompanied by fear and avoidance when facing the disease, which in turn aggravates negative emotions, affects treatment compliance, affects recovery, and reduces quality of life. Cao et al. (2017) studied that poor disease management of diabetic patients is often accompanied by a variety of bad habits, such as lack of healthy diet, poor medication compliance, lack of disease awareness, etc., which can affect treatment compliance. sex, delaying disease recovery, increasing the risk of adverse events, aggravating the condition, and ultimately affecting their quality of life (Ni et al., 2017). In addition, patients with poor disease management levels lack awareness of the disease, are unable to recognize the harm the disease brings to their health, have difficulty making healthy behavioural changes, and have poor enthusiasm for treatment, which in turn leads to continued aggravation of the disease and increases the difficulty of treatment. Affect patients' quality of life (Zhao et al., 2017). Previous studies reported that nearly 88.5% of Chinese patients with diabetes failed to achieve blood glucose control (Yang et al., 2020). T2DM patients perform poorly in blood glucose monitoring, which seriously affects their ability to control the disease and respond to emergencies, and affects the patient's quality of life. Good disease management behaviors can affect the blood sugar control level of diabetic patients. Patients can correctly manage their disease and have enough confidence to achieve disease management goals, which is extremely important for improving their quality of life (Ji et al., 2014; Xia et al., 2022). Studies such as Huang Jin (Huang et al., 2013) and Sun Shengnan (Sun et al., 2013) also pointed out that strengthening diabetes education and improving patients' diabetes management knowledge and skills can improve patients' disease management behaviors, thereby improving the quality of diabetes patients. Quality of life level. Therefore, for patients with type 2 diabetes, health education and psychological intervention should be strengthened during treatment to improve the patient's emotional state and self-management level, so as to promote the disease outcome and improve the patient's quality of life.

Conclusions

This study confirms that quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes is indeed significantly related to patient disease management outcomes, specifically in terms of glycemic control and complication prevention in patients with type 2 diabetes, as a result of treatment adherence scores. . Correlation analysis is mainly used to explore the relationship between disease management outcomes and health-related quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes.

In terms of diabetes disease management, 97.88% of the respondents were initially diagnosed with diabetes. Most of the respondents used fasting blood glucose as the last way to measure blood glucose. In terms of treatment compliance, the average score was low, which indicates the impact of type 2 Regarding the quality of life of diabetic patients, a considerable number of respondents use medications to control blood sugar, but this also indicates that blood sugar control is not good. In terms of quality of life, respondents rated their happiness as low. The area with the highest scores was the social relationships

domain. The area with the lowest scores was the psychological domain. Specifically, in the psychological domain, the emotional state and self-satisfaction of the respondents are key factors to pay attention to because they elicit negative reactions. In terms of the association of variables with quality of life, patients with poorer glycemic control had lower QOL scores. The psychological domain score was related to complication prevention, and the environmental domain score was affected by diabetes complications and treatment compliance, as those with complications and poor treatment compliance had the lowest scores.

In order to correctly interpret the results of this study, some limitations should be acknowledged. Due to the limited sample size, the study results may deviate from reality. This study is a correlational study that only explores the relationship between type 2 diabetes and patients' quality of life, so it cannot directly improve patients' quality of life. This study also has certain limitations. If the impact of disease management level on the long-term prognosis of patients with type 2 diabetes was not observed, more in-depth research on patients with type 2 diabetes is still needed in the future, focusing on analysing the impact of disease management level on the long-term prognosis of patients with type 2 diabetes. improvement effect.

Recommendations

According to the study's conclusions, glycemic control and complication prevention are important factors in improving the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes. Therefore, we should pay more attention to patients with type 2 diabetes, control their blood sugar levels, and delay the occurrence and development of complications, so as to improve the quality of life. Based on the above conclusions, the recommendations are put forward:

- (1) Strengthen blood sugar monitoring. Strengthen multi-point blood sugar monitoring on fasting and two hours after meals, with special focus on blood sugar levels during the period of adjusting medications or switching to insulin, to fully understand blood sugar control.
- (2) Pay attention to mental health. Use non-invasive and economical scales to screen for anxiety and depression in diabetic patients; provide psychological counselling to patients with these conditions, and at the same time provide patients with more care and improve negative emotions.
- (3) Pay attention to health education. Strengthen the standardised diagnosis and treatment training of diabetes for medical staff, especially for grassroots medical staff, continuously improve the quality of health education for diabetic patients, improve patient satisfaction, prevent the occurrence and development of complications, and improve patients' disease management levels, thereby helping patients improve their Quality of Life.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers got an ethical clearance from the Ethics Review Committee and Institutional Review Board. The researchers informed consent from participants by

disclosing information regarding the study before they made an informed decision, facilitating understanding and promoting their voluntariness. The participants proceed to answer the survey once they agree and sign the informed consent. Participants can freely withdraw from the study without any questions and potential loss of any benefits. The data is electronically stored and protected and does not include the name of the participants which means there is no way that data analysis can be traced back to the participants. The data was accessed by the research team for data analysis and stored as a computer file a year after publication for reference and will then be deleted. Data and statistics will be published for public access.

The researchers do not see any conflicts of interest in this work. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research. The authors would also like to declare that this research was not funded and conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest and was purely research in nature.

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REFERENCES

- Cao Hongwei, Chen Jing, Gan Yu, & Dai Lu. (2017). Study on the self-management behavior and blood sugar control status of patients with type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Aerospace Medicine*, 28(11), 1397-1398.
- Chang Qiong. Analysis of the relationship between medication compliance and cerebral infarction in elderly patients with diabetes mellitus[J]. *Journal of Integrated Traditional Chinese and Western Medicine for Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Diseases*, 2018, 16(3): 378-380.
- Chen Ailing, Zhang Zhenlu, Liao Zhihong, Wan Lihong, Deng Wanping, & Yuan Yonghong. (2006). Correlation between self-management level and quality of life in patients with diabetes. *Chinese Journal of Behavioral Medical Science*, 15(5), 434-436.
- Chen Limei, Wang Yuehua, Huang Xia, & Dong Caimei. (2015). Correlation between care burden and quality of life of family caregivers of diabetic patients. *Nursing Research: Mid-term Edition*, 29(5), 1692-1695.
- Dickerson, F., Wohlheiter, K., Medoff, D., Fang, L., Kreyenbuhl, J., Goldberg, R., ... & Dixon, L. (2011). Predictors of quality of life in type 2 diabetes patients with schizophrenia, major mood disorder, and without mental illness. *Quality of Life Research*, 20, 1419-1425.
- Donald, M., Dower, J., Coll, J. R., Baker, P., Mukandi, B., & Doi, S. A. (2013). Mental health issues decrease diabetes-specific quality of life independent of glycaemic control and

- complications: findings from Australia's living with diabetes cohort study. *Health and quality of life outcomes*, 11, 1-8.
- Fan Lifeng, Huang Yurong, & Li Haiyan. (1996). Quality of life and influencing factors of diabetic patients. *Chinese Journal of Nursing*, 31(10), 562-567.
- Gao Yu, & Xue Weiduo . (2023). Effects of health education led by family contracted doctors on health literacy and self-management behavior of community diabetic patients. *Medical Clinical Research*, 40(1), 127-129.
- Guariguata, L., Whiting, D. R., Hambleton, I., Beagley, J., Linnenkamp, U., & Shaw, J. E. (2014). Global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2013 and projections for 2035. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*, 103(2), 137-149.
- Huang Jin, Liu Yuehua, Zhang Yan, & Yao Hui. (2013). Correlation between self-management status and diabetes knowledge and attitudes in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Central South University: Medical Science*, 38(2), 176-181.
- Ji JJ, Liu L, Lou QQ, Yuan XD, Yao P, & Zhang DY. (2014). Study on the self-management behavior and blood sugar control status of patients with type 2 diabetes. *Chinese Journal of Nursing*, 49(5), 617-620.
- Li Minghui. Improvement effect of diabetes health management on nursing compliance and quality of life of patients [J]. *Chinese Science and Technology Journal Database (full-text edition) Medicine and Health*, 2023(9):0001-0004
- Li X J. (2020). Influence of diabetes health education on treatment compliance and quality of life in patients with endocrine care. *Electronic Journal of Practical Clinical Nursing*, 5(6), 1.
- Li Xueqin, & Cai Hongwei. (2004). Investigation on compliance behavior of diabetic patients receiving out-of-hospital treatment. *Chinese Journal of Nursing*, 39(7), 500-502.
- Liang Y M. (2020). Research progress of self-management behavior in elderly patients with diabetes mellitus. *Nursing of Integrated Chinese and Western Medicine (Chinese and English)*, 6(5), 3.
- Liang, M. H. (2014). Study on the quality of life and its influencing factors of patients with type 2 diabetes in Beijing community (Doctoral dissertation, Beijing: Beijing University of Chinese Medicine).
- Liu J, & Wang H. (2016). Study on the quality of life and related factors of patients with type 2 diabetes in the community of Changsha. *Nursing Research: Mid-term Edition*, 30(11), 4016-4019.
- Liu, M.J., Lin, M.J., Zhou, Q.L., Wang, J., Liang, T., & Zhang, Y. (2020). Effect of phased health education based on the change law of compliance curve in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Chinese Journal of Health Education*, 36(1), 89-95.
- Neumann, A., Schoffer, O., Norström, F., Norberg, M., Klug, S. J., & Lindholm, L. (2014). Health-related quality of life for pre-diabetic states and type 2 diabetes mellitus: a cross-sectional study in Västerbotten Sweden. *Health and quality of life outcomes*, 12, 1-10.
- Ni Yunxia, Liu Suzhen, Diao Yongshu, Li Jiping, Dong Ting, & Tao Lin. (2017). Analysis of quality of life and influencing factors of 1796 community patients with diabetes in Sichuan Province. *Nursing Research: Early Edition*, (8), 2707-2711.
- Rose, M., Fliege, H., Hildebrandt, M., Schirop, T., & Klapp, B. F. (2002). The network of psychological variables in patients with diabetes and their importance for quality of life and metabolic control. *Diabetes care*, 25(1), 35-42.
- Rubin, R. R., & Peyrot, M. (1999). Quality of life and diabetes. *Diabetes/metabolism research and reviews*, 15(3), 205-218.
- Sun Shengnan, Zhao Weigang, Dong Yingyue, & Li Zheng. (2011). Analysis of the current status and influencing factors of self-management in patients with diabetes. *Chinese Journal of Nursing*, 46(3), 229-233.
- Tang P, Peng Y H. (2023). Correlation between compliance level and quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Psychology*, 18(6), 31-33.

- Wang Feiying, Li Jing, Yang Ying, Liu Xiaoyan, Xiong Yuxin, & Feng Yunhua. (2015). Study on the quality of life and influencing factors of patients with type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Kunming Medical University*, 36(3), 83-87.
- WHOQoL Group. (1994). The development of the World Health Organization quality of life assessment instrument (the WHOQOL). In *Quality of Life Assessment: International Perspectives: Proceedings of the Joint-Meeting Organized by the World Health Organization and the Fondation IPSEN in Paris, July 2–3, 1993* (pp. 41-57). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Xia Z, Jiang Y, Mao F, Dong WL, Zhang WW, & Dong JQ. (2022). Changes in quality of life and its influencing factors of self-management of diabetes patients in six provinces and cities in China during a two-year follow-up. *Chinese Journal of Public Health*, 38(3), 285-290.
- Yang Qingping, Wu Cui, Wu Xiaoqiong, Wu Fei, Cheng Minna, Yan Qinghua, ... & Li Yanyun. (2020). Analysis of the current status of comprehensive management and control of diabetes in Shanghai communities. *Internal Medicine Theory and Practice*, 15(2), 116-119.
- Yu Junfeng. Effect of diversified nursing on treatment compliance, complication rate and quality of life in patients with diabetes and coronary heart disease[J]. *Electronic Journal of Integrated Traditional Chinese and Western Medicine for Cardiovascular Diseases*, 2018, 6(16): 121,124.
- Yu Yuanyuan& Xie Hong. (2017). Research progress on factors affecting quality of life in patients with T2DM. *Journal of Mudanjiang Medical College*, 38(5): 132-134,128.
- Zhang Dudan, Tang Xun, Jin Danyao, Hu Yonghua, & Gao Pei. (2018). Meta-analysis of diabetes prevalence in Chinese adults. *Chinese Journal of Epidemiology*, 39(6), 852-857.
- Zheng QW, Che Q Z, Yang J T, & Chen D F. (2020). Progress in precision health management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Chronic disease prevention and Control in China* (2), 6.
- Zhuang Western, Tian Bingjie, Wang Qi, Fu Jia, & Yang Xiaoli. (2021). Quality of life status and influencing factors in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes. *Shanghai Nursing*, 21(2), 5.